

IKKINCHI JAHON URUSHIDAN SO'NG YAPONIYADAGI MADANIY VA IJTIMOY MEROS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15740595>

Kirish. Ikkinchi Jahon Urushi insoniyat tarixidagi eng halokatli mojarolardan biri bo'lib, u ko'plab davlatlar qatori Yaponiyaning ham siyosiy, ijtimoiy va madaniy hayotiga chuqur ta'sir ko'rsatdi. 1945-yilda urush yakunlangach, Yaponiya G'arb tomonidan, xususan, AQSh boshchiligidagi ittifoqchi davlatlar nazorati ostiga o'tdi. Bu bosqichda mamlakatda demokratik islohotlar, iqtisodiy qayta qurishlar va madaniy yangilanishlar boshlangan bo'lsa-da, yapon xalqining an'anaviy qadriyatlari va madaniy merosi saqlab qolindi hamda yangi davrga moslashtirildi. Ikkinchi jahon urushidan so'ng Yaponiya vayronaga aylangan davlatlardan biri edi.

Ammo oradan atigi 20–30 yil o'tgach, bu mamlakat jahonning yetakchi iqtisodiyotlari safidan joy oldi. Bu holat tarixda “Yapon mo'jizasi” nomi bilan tilga olinadi. Ushbu mo'jiza nafaqat iqtisodiy yuksalishni, balki siyosiy va madaniy jihatdan ham taraqqiy etgan model bo'lib, u dunyo tarixida chuqur iz qoldirgan. Yaponiyaning tiklanish va yuksalish jarayoni 1945-yildan 1990-yillargacha davom etgan bo'lib, u bir necha bosqichlarda kechdi. Uning asosiy jihatlari quyidagilardan iborat: Urushdan keyin Yaponiya sanoati butkul yemirilgan edi. AQSh tomonidan ko'rsatilgan iqtisodiy yordam, islohotlar (agrar islohotlar, yirik kompaniyalarni qayta tashkil etish) va mehnatga asoslangan jamiyat bu davrda poydevor bo'ldi. Yaponiya eksportga yo'naltirilgan industrial strategiya yordamida avtomobilsozlik, elektronika, kema qurish sohalarida dunyoda yetakchilikka erishdi. Neft inqiroziga qarshi energiya samaradorligi va yuqori texnologiyali ishlab chiqarishga o'tish, inson kapitaliga sarmoya va korporativ boshqaruvdagi izchillik Yaponiya mo'jizasining asosiy omillari bo'ldi.

Urushdan keyingi davrda G'arb ta'sirining kuchayishiga qaramay, yaponlar o'zlarining asrlar davomida shakllangan madaniy an'analarini asrab-avaylashga katta e'tibor qaratdilar.

Xususan, Kabuki va Noh teatr san'ati, ikebana (gullarni artistik joylashtirish san'ati), choy marosimi (chado) va kaligrafiya kabi an'anaviy san'at turlari yana jonlantirildi va ommalashtirildi.

Madaniy va ijtimoiy meros. Yapon mo'jizasi nafaqat iqtisodiy, balki madaniy va ijtimoiy jihatdan ham ta'sirli bo'ldi:

- Ish madaniyati (hayot-makon korporatsiyalar, butun umr ish bilan bandlik);
- Ta'lim tizimining yuqori sifati;
- Innovatsiyalarga ochiqlik;
- Milliy qadriyatlar va g'ururning saqlanishi global kapitalizm bilan uyg'unlashgan holda mavjud bo'ldi.

Ikkinchi jahon urushi insoniyat tarixidagi eng vayronkor va fojeali urush bo'ldi.

Ayniqsa, 1945-yilning 6-avgust kuni AQSh tomonidan Yaponiyaning Xirosima shahriga tashlangan atom bombasi minglab begunoh insonlar hayotiga zomin bo'ldi. Urushning bu qurolli jinoyati nafaqat jismoniy vayronagarchilik, balki ruhiy jarohatlar ham qoldirdi. Ushbu fojeaning eng ta'sirli ramzlaridan biri — Sadako Sasaki va uning ming qog'oz turnasi bo'ldi. Bugungi kunda bu voqea nafaqat Yaponiya, balki butun dunyo uchun tinchlik va umid ramziga aylangan.

Sadako Sasaki — atom fojeasining timsoli

Sadako Sasaki 1943-yil Xirosima shahrida tug'ilgan. U ikki yoshida Xirosimaga tashlangan atom bombasi portlashi vaqtida shahar markazidan taxminan ikki kilometr uzoqlikda bo'lgan. O'sha damda tirik qolgan bo'lsa-da, oradan o'n yil o'tgach, Sadakoda leykemiya (oq qon kasalligi) aniqlandi. Bu kasallik ko'plab atom bombasi qurbonlarida keyinchalik paydo bo'lgan bo'lib, u "atom bombasi kasalligi" deb ham ataladi.

Ming qog'oz turna afsonasi va Sadakoning orzusi

Yapon xalq e'tiqodida mingta qog'ozdan yasalgan turna qushi (orizuru) tayyorlagan odamning istagi ro'yobga chiqadi, deb hisoblanadi. Sadako hayotining so'nggi kunlarida shunday orzuga — tuzalish umidiga tayangan holda turna yasashni boshlaydi. Ba'zi manbalarga ko'ra, u 644 ta turnani yasagan, boshqalar esa uning mingdan ortiq turna yasaganini yozadi.

Turna yasash Sadako uchun nafaqat ruhiy taskin, balki tinchlik, sabr-toqat va umid timsoli edi. U hatto o'zining do'stlari va kasalxona hamkasblari uchun ham turnalar yasagan.

Xotira haykali: Tinchlikka chaqiriq

1958-yilda Xirosimada Bolalar Tinchlik Haykali (Children's Peace Monument) ochildi.

Bu haykal Sadako Sasaki va atom bombasi qurboni bo'lgan barcha bolalarga bag'ishlangan. Haykalda ikki qo'lni yuqoriga ko'targan qizaloq — Sadako — tasvirlangan, uning qo'lida esa katta qog'oz turna qushi bor. Haykalning poydevorida shunday yozuv bor:

"Bu bizning faryodimiz. Bu bizning duomiz. Tinchlik uchun tinimsiz harakat qilaylik."

Har yili 6-avgust kuni — Xirosimaga bomba tashlangan kun — dunyoning turli nuqtalaridan yoshlar ushbu haykal oldiga minglab rangli qog'oz turnalarni keltiradilar. Bu an'ana hali-hanuz davom etmoqda.

Sadakoning o'rni va ramziy ma'nosi. Sadakoning hayoti va vafoti nafaqat fojea, balki insoniyatga saboq bo'la oldi. Uning hikoyasi quyidagi qadriyatlarni o'zida mujassam etadi:

- Tinchliksevarlik — urushga qarshi insoniy da'vat;
- Umid va sabr — og'ir sinovlarga qaramay yashashga intilish;
- Insonparvarlik — global hamjihatlikni qo'llab-quvvatlashga chaqiriq.

Sadakoning hikoyasi bugungi kunda maktablarda, tinchlik targ'ibot markazlarida, muzeylarda, filmlar va kitoblar orqali targ'ib qilinmoqda.

Xulosa. Sadako va uning ming qog'oz turnasi nafaqat bir bolaning fojeasini, balki insoniyatning urushsiz kelajak sari intilishini anglatadi. Bu hikoya bugun ham dolzarbligini yo'qotmagan: u har bir kishiga tinchlikning qadri, umid va insoniylik haqida o'ylashga undaydi. Sadako — tinchlik, sabr-toqat va global birdamlik ramzidir. Uning xotirasi orqali butun insoniyat urushlarning oldini olish, yadroviy qurolni yo'q qilish, tinch hayot kechirish g'oyalari yodda saqlashi zarur. Yapon mo'jizasi — insoniyat tarixidagi eng yirik iqtisodiy tiklanish hodisalaridan biridir.

Uning tarixdagi o‘rni nafaqat raqamlar va iqtisodiy ko‘rsatkichlarda, balki xalq irodasi, madaniyat va milliy yuksalish namunasi sifatida saqlanib qolgan. Bugungi kunda ushbu model ko‘plab rivojlanayotgan mamlakatlar tomonidan o‘rganilmoqda va moslashtirilmoqda.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

1. **Johnson, Chalmers.** *MITI and the Japanese Miracle: The Growth of Industrial Policy, 1925–1975.* Stanford University Press, 1982.
2. **Ohno, Kenichi.** *The Economic Development of Japan: The Path Traveled by Japan as a Developing Country.* GRIPS Development Forum, 2006.
3. **Nakamura, Takafusa.** *The Postwar Japanese Economy: Its Development and Structure.* University of Tokyo Press, 1995.
4. Yuldosheva, F. (2024). MIRZO ULUG‘BEK KUTUBXONASI VA BUGUNGI TAQDIRI. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(12), 741–749. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/-research/article/view/58564>
5. Yuldosheva F. (2024). BOLA TUG‘ILISHI BILAN BOG‘LIQ MAROSIMLAR O‘ZBEK XALQI HAYOTINING AJRALMAS QISMI SIFATIDA. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(11), 788–791. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/48058>
6. Yuldosheva F. Y. qizi. (2023). LEV NIKOLAYEVICH GUMILYOVNING “QADIMGI TURKLAR” ASARIDA KO‘KTURKLAR YODGORLIKLARI XUSUSIDA. *GOLDEN BRAIN*, 1(16), 338–342. Retrieved from <https://researchedu.org/index.php//article/view/3908>
7. Yuldosheva F. (2025). MAHMUDXO‘JA BEHBUDIY – MILLATNING O‘Z TAQDIRINI ANGLASHIDA YORQIN YULDUZ VA MILLIY UYG‘ONISH DAVRINING RAMZI. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(1), 420–427. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/scienceresearch/article/view/60832>
8. Yuldosheva, F. & Abdihamidova, F. . (2025). BEHBUDIYNI KIM O‘LDIRGAN?. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(1), 359–366. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/63681>
9. Yuldosheva, F. . (2025). IBN BATTUTANING “SAYOHATNOMA” ASARI MUHIM MANBA SIFATIDA. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(2), 573–580. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/scienceresearch/article/view/66954>
10. Yarashova, M., Yuldosheva, F., & Haqqulov, M. (2025). TA‘LIM OLIH TARTIBI: YANGILANISH VA O‘ZGARISHLAR. MASOFAVIY, DUAL VA INKLYUZIV TA‘LIM. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(2), 73–80. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/70712>
11. Haqqulov, M., Yarashova, M., & Yuldosheva, F. (2025). TARIXIY KARTOGRAFIYANING ASOSIY YO‘NALISHLARI, SHAKLLANISHI VA TARAQQIYOTI. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(2), 81–91. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/70714>
12. Yuldosheva, F., Haqqulov, M., & Yarashova, M. (2025). QADIMGI TURKIY XALQLARDA “QUT” MAROSIMI XUSUSIDA. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(3),

- 132–136. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/scienceresearch/article/view/72375>
13. Yuldosheva, F. (2025). ZARDUSHTIYLIK DINI MAROSIMLARI HAQIDA. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(2), 5–12. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/70963>
14. Xayrullayev U., Xayrullayev U., Muyidinov, B., & Yuldosheva, F. (2025). POLSHANING I JAHON URUSHIDAN KEYINGI AHVOLI. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(4), 36–48. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/scienceresearch/article/view/77250>
15. Yuldosheva, F., Muyiddinov, B., & Xayrullayev, U. (2025). AMIR TEMUR VORISLARI: SIYOSIY, HARBIY VA MADANIY MEROSNING DAVOMIYLIGI. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(4), 17–26. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/77244>
16. Yuldosheva, F., Muyiddinov, B., & Xayrullayev, U. (2025). JAHONDA KINO SAN'ATINING RIVOJI VA ARXIV HUIJATLARINING SHAKLLANISHI. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(4), 27–35. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/77247>
17. Yuldosheva, F. ., & Abdilhamidova , F. (2025). AMIR TEMUR VA UNING DAVRIDA MADANIYAT SOHASIDA AMALGA OSHIRILGAN ISHLAR. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(3), 458–467. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/74115>
18. Yuldosheva , F., & Asadova , S. (2025). IKKINCHI JAHON URUSHIDA O'ZBEK AYOLLARINING ISHTIROKI. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(4), 389–396. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/81334>
19. Yuldosheva, F. (2025). IKKINCHI JAHON URUSHIDA O'ZBEKISTONNING QO'SHGAN HISSASI. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(4), 1648–1655. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/81178>
20. Yarashova, M., Muyiddinov, B., & Yuldosheva, F. (2025). RAQAMLASHTIRISH OMILLARI:KELAJAK ASOSIY SOHASI. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(5), 101–110. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/85863>
21. Yarashova, M., Muyiddinov, B. ., & Yuldosheva, F. . (2025). TADQIQOTLARDA MANBALARNI O'RGANISH: ANIQLASH, TIKLASH, TAHLIL QILISHNING AHAMIYATI. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(5), 238–245. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/85827>
22. Yuldosheva , F. (2025). XUMAY ONA TIMSOLI: TARIX, AFSONA VA MA'NAVIYAT QO'SHILMASI. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(5), 223–229. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/85822>
23. Yarashova, M., Yuldosheva, F. ., & Xayrullayev, U. . (2025). IJTIMOIIY TARMOQLARNING MEDIA MAKONDAGI O'RNI. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(5), 674–685. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/87657>

24. Srojeva, G. (2025). MIRZO MUHAMMAD HAYDARNING “TARIXI RASHIDIY” ASARIDA O’RTA OSIYO TARIXINI O’RGANISHDA MUHIM MANBA SIFATIDA. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(1), 531-539.
25. Srojeva, G., & Ormonova, M. (2025). BUXORO SHAHRIDAGI ARK QO’RG’ONI, SITORAI MOHI XOSA, XO’JA SAROY ME’MORIY YODGORLIKLARI. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(1), 533-544.
26. Srojeva, G. (2024). Solutions, Results And Problems Of Reforms In The Field Of Education. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(1), 782-788.
27. Srojeva, G. (2023). Lower Zarafshan Oasis Tourism Opportunities. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(10), 199-204.
28. Srojeva, G. (2024). EFFECTIVE FORMS OF SPIRITUAL AND MORAL EDUCATION AND EDUCATIONAL WORK IN A PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTION. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(2), 247-253.
29. Srojeva, G. (2024). Strengthening The Material And Technical Base Of Preschool Education And Training Institutions. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(2), 673-681.
30. Srojeva, G. (2024). The Canadian Economy During The Global Economic Crisis. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(2), 57-63.
31. Srojeva, G. (2024). International Cooperation In The Field Of Education. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(2), 1041-1050.
32. Vahobovna, S. G. (2023). Quyidagi Zarafshon Vohasi Turizm Imkoniyatlari.
33. Srojeva, G. (2024). Attention Paid To Preschool Educational Institutions In New Uzbekistan. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(2), 258-266.
34. Srojeva, G. (2023). Continuity In Education-Chief Mezon. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(12), 834-839.
35. Gulbahor, S. (2023). Continuity In Education-Chief Mezon. *Modern Science and Research*, 2, 834-839.
36. Vahobovna, S. G. (2024). Canada during the world economic crisis of 1929-1933. *Ta’lim Va Rivojlanish Tahlili Onlayn Ilmiy Jurnal*, 4(4), 48-54.
37. Vahobovna, S. G. (2024). Role of Preschool Educational Institutions in Education of a Perfect Person. *European Journal Of Innovation In Nonformal Education*, 4(3), 208-214.
38. Srojeva, G. (2024). 1929-1932-YILLARDAGI JAHON IQTISODIY INQIROZI DAVRIDA YAPONIYA. *Nrj*, 1(2), 118-128.
39. Yarashova, M., Sa’dullayev, U., & Yo’ldosheva, F. (2025). BUXORO VOHASI AYOLLARINING AN’ANAVIY BOSH KIYIMLARI- DO’PPI VA RO’MOL. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(1), 600–607. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/64116>
40. Yarashova, M., & Sultonova, M. (2025). BUXORO VOHASI DAFN MAROSIMI KIYIMLARI VA ULAR BILAN BOG’LIQ IRIM-SIRIMLAR. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(1), 352–358. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/63674>
41. Yarashova, M. (2025). EDVARD TAYLOR –ETNOLOGIYADA EVOLYUTIONISTIK MAKTAB ASOSCHISI. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(2),

- 1005–1012. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/68483>
42. Yarashova, M., Yuldosheva, F., & Haqqulov, M. (2025). TA'LIM OLISH TARTIBI: YANGILANISH VA O'ZGARISHLAR. MASOFAVIY, DUAL VA INKLYUZIV TA'LIM. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(2), 73–80. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/70712>
43. Haqqulov, M., Yarashova, M., & Yuldosheva, F. (2025). TARIXIY KARTOGRAFIYANING ASOSIY YO'NALISHLARI, SHAKLLANISHI VA TARAQQIYOTI. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(2), 81–91. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/70714>
44. Gulyamov, A., Yarashova, M., & Karimov, S. . (2025). O'RTA ASRLARDA G'ARBIY YEVIYOPADA SHAHAR-QAL'A, SHAHAR-CHEKOV, SAVDO O'BYEKTI AHAMIYATIGA OID SHAHARLARNING VUJUDGA KELISHI. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(3), 122–131. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/71868>
45. Yarashova , M. . (2025). IBN ARABIYNING INSON BORLIG'IGA DOIR QARASHLARI: ILM, RUH VA HAQIQAT. *Общественные науки в современном мире: теоретические и практические исследования*, 4(1), 72–74. извлечено от <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/zdif/article/view/64262>
46. Gulyamov, A., Yarashova, M., & Karimov, S. (2025). РОЛЬ ХАНА УЗБЕКА В РАСПРОСТРАНЕНИИ ИСЛАМА В ЗОЛОТОЙ ОРДЕ. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(3), 146–154. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/72380>
47. Yuldosheva, F., Haqqulov, M., & Yarashova, M. (2025). QADIMGI TURKIY XALQLARDA “QUT” MAROSIMI XUSUSIDA. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(3), 132–136. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/72375>
48. Yarashova M., & Rahimova, N. (2025). JADIDCHILARNING MA'RIFATPARVARLIK HARAKATLARI VA ULARNING XALQ MA'NAVIYATINI YUKSALTIRISHDAGI O'RNI. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(3), 398–408. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/7306>
49. Yarashova, M. (2025). TAQINCHOQLAR VA ULARNING AHOLI ETNIK HAYOTIDA TUTGAN O'RNI. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(3), 778–790. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/72864>
50. Gulyamov, A., Yarashova, M., & Karimov, S. (2025). BUXORO VOHASIDA MATO VA MATO TAYYORLASH USULLARI. PAXTA. G'UZAK. JUN. XALAJI. BO'Z. OLACHA. BEQASAM. BAXMAL. ADRAS. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(3), 330–340. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/73808>
51. Xayrullayev , U., Sadullayev, U. ., Yarashova, M., & Boltayev, O. (2025). XIX ASR OXIRI XX ASR BOSHLARIDA QO'SHNI DAVLATLARNING POLSHAGA

- NISBATAN YURITGAN SIYOSATI. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(3), 420–432. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/74107>
52. Yarashova, M., & Rahimova, N. (2025). FAYZULLA XO'JAYEV ILMIY FAOLIYATINING DASTLABKI DAVRI. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(3), 448–457. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/74113>
53. Boltayev, O., Yarashova, M., Xayrullayev, U., & Sadullayev, U. (2025). OYROT QABILASI VA ULARNING DAVLATCHILIK ASOSLARING SHAKLANISHIGA UMUMIY TAVSIF. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(3), 600–608. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/75573>
54. Yarashova, M., Boltayev, O., Xayrullayev, U., & Sadullayev, U. (2025). BUXORO VOHASI AYOLLARINING AN'ANAVIY LIBOSLARI (XIX ASR OXIRI XX ASR BOSHLARIDA). *Modern Science and Research*, 4(3), 571–581. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/75785>